

THE FUNCTION OF THE ASSET RECOVERY AGENCY OF THE ATTORNEY GENERAL'S OFFICE OF THE REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA IN HANDLING CONFISCATED OBJECTS AND CONFISCATED GOODS PROCEEDINGS OF CRIME

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Abstract

The recovery of assets resulting from criminal acts is an integral part of the modern law enforcement system, which emphasizes not only the punishment of perpetrators but also the recovery of state losses and social justice. In the Indonesian context, the establishment of the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA) under the Attorney General's Office is a strategic step in addressing the challenges of asset recovery in a systematic and integrated manner. This study aims to analyze the nature of the handling of confiscated and seized assets resulting from criminal acts, evaluate the authority of the BPA of the Attorney General's Office, and develop an effective inter-institutional settlement model for managing these assets. The method used is normative legal research with a legislative, conceptual, and comparative approach. Data sources come from laws and regulations, institutional documents, and scientific literature, analyzed descriptively and qualitatively. The results show that although the BPA has strong structural and legal legitimacy, the implementation of asset recovery still faces various obstacles, including overlapping authority between institutions, lengthy legal processes, and regulatory weaknesses related to confiscation without conviction. Inter-institutional synergy and the strengthening of a measurable and accountable national asset recovery system are needed. In conclusion, optimizing the function of the Attorney General's BPA is crucial in supporting law enforcement based on justice and benefit, while also ensuring the return of state assets for the greatest prosperity of the people.

Keywords: Asset Recovery, Confiscated Objects, Confiscated Goods, Prosecutor's Office, Authority, Criminal Law, BPA.

INTRODUCTION

Criminal law enforcement in Indonesia has undergone a fundamental transformation along with the increasing complexity of crimes, especially economic crimes such as corruption, money laundering, and transnational crimes (Apriliansah et al., 2025; Djunarjanto et al., 2025; Sugianto et al., 2025). Handling criminal acts is no longer sufficient by simply imposing criminal sanctions on the perpetrators, but must be accompanied by steps to restore the losses experienced by the state (Ali et al., 2022; Awaliah Nasution et al., 2022; Mayans-Hermida et al., 2023). Within the framework of a state based on the rule of law, asset recovery is an integral part of the criminal justice system, which upholds substantive justice and restorative justice. At the global level, countries are encouraged to strengthen their legal frameworks in order to narrow the scope of action for perpetrators of economic crimes, especially through the instrument of confiscation and seizure of assets resulting from criminal acts (Fedorov et al., 2025; Lyudmila et al., 2021; Pasechnyk et al., 2025). Indonesia, as part of the international

community, has ratified the United Nations Convention against Corruption (UNCAC) through Law Number 7 of 2006, which mandates state parties to establish an effective system for tracking, confiscating, and recovering assets. Consequently, Indonesia must adopt and implement these international principles into national law.

In response to this, the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia established a special unit called the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA) based on Attorney General's Regulation Number 3 of 2024, replacing the Asset Recovery Center (PPA), which previously had a limited structure. The establishment of the BPA reflects institutional strengthening and affirmation of authority in carrying out the functions of tracing, freezing, confiscating, and seizing assets resulting from criminal acts in a coordinated and integrated manner. The BPA serves as the state's spearhead in efforts to recover state financial losses through legitimate and measurable legal mechanisms.

However, in its implementation, asset recovery in Indonesia still faces various problems. These include a lack of integration between law enforcement agencies such as the Attorney General's Office, the Police, the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (through the RUPBASAN), and the Ministry of Finance (through the DJKN), weak technical regulations on non-conviction-based forfeiture, and lengthy procedures for executing court decisions related to asset recovery. These realities hinder the optimization of the state's role in securing public assets that should be used for the greatest possible prosperity of the people.

From a legal perspective, there is still overlapping authority and unclear delineation of functions between institutions. In some cases, confiscated objects are neglected at the RUPBASAN (State Property Repository) or are slowly managed as state confiscated goods due to a lack of systemic coordination. However, normatively, the Prosecutor's Office, as the *dominus litis*, holds a strategic position not only in the prosecution phase but also in the implementation of decisions and the execution of evidence and criminal assets. The lack of clear procedures and an integrated system is one of the causes of inefficient asset recovery in Indonesia.

This situation is exacerbated by the non-passage of the Criminal Asset Confiscation Bill, a crucial legal instrument supporting an effective asset recovery strategy. Without a strong legal basis, the state faces difficulties in prosecuting assets hidden, diverted, or laundered in complex schemes, especially those involving foreign jurisdictions (Arianto, 2024; Iheme, 2021; Kartika et al., 2021). Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the legal framework and governance of asset recovery based on the principles of effectiveness, accountability, and justice (Pantoli, 2024; Pratama et al., 2025; Soeherman et al., 2024).

A number of previous studies have addressed the issue of asset recovery, but most have focused on the normative level or limited themselves to the role of the judiciary in general. While research by Meggie Regina Imbar, Safrin Ritonga, and Titin Herawati Utara has made important contributions to understanding the dynamics of asset recovery, it has not comprehensively examined the institutional shift from the Asset Recovery Center to the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA), including its impact on inter-agency coordination and adaptive

models for handling confiscated and seized assets to meet the needs of the contemporary legal system.

Based on this background, this study aims to: (1) Identify and explain the nature of handling confiscated objects and seized goods resulting from criminal acts from a national and international legal perspective; (2) Analyze the authority of the Asset Recovery Agency of the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia in implementing state asset recovery; and (3) Develop an inter-institutional settlement model in the management of confiscated objects and seized goods that is effective, efficient, and equitable.

METHOD

This research uses a normative juridical approach, namely a legal research method that is based on a literature review of positive legal norms, legal principles, legal principles, and relevant legal theories (Rizkia et al., 2023; Suyanto, 2023). This approach was chosen because the main research problem concerns the analysis of the authority of the Asset Recovery Agency of the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia based on applicable laws and regulations, as well as the formulation of an inter-institutional settlement model in the management of confiscated objects and seized goods resulting from criminal acts.

This research also uses a conceptual and comparative approach. The conceptual approach is intended to examine legal doctrines developing in academic literature in order to understand the nature of authority, asset recovery, and the principles of justice in criminal law and state administration (Azhar, 2022). A comparative approach is used to analyze asset recovery practices in other countries such as the Netherlands, South Korea, and the United States as a comparison to develop an institutional and coordination model that is relevant to the legal context in Indonesia (Setiawan, 2024).

The types and sources of data in this study consist of:

- 1) Primary legal materials, namely laws and regulations such as the Criminal Procedure Code, the Attorney General's Law, the Money Laundering Eradication Law, Presidential Regulation Number 15 of 2024, and the Attorney General's Regulation regarding the organization and authority of the BPA.
- 2) Secondary legal materials, in the form of legal literature, scientific journals, previous research results, and the views of administrative and criminal law experts.
- 3) Tertiary legal materials, such as legal dictionaries, legal encyclopedias, and other supporting sources.

The data collection technique is carried out through document studies (documentary studies), namely a systematic review of legal and non-legal documents that are relevant to the object of study (Arifuddin et al., 2025). This technique involves examining official state documents, academic papers, legislative results, and court decisions related to the seizure and confiscation of criminal assets.

The data analysis technique was descriptive-qualitative, namely outlining the content and meaning of the legal materials studied, then analyzed systematically to find the logical structure, disharmony of norms, and potential relevant legal interpretations to support the research argument. The analysis was conducted deductively, starting from general theories regarding authority, administrative law, and criminal law, to then draw conclusions regarding the concrete practice of asset recovery by the Indonesian Attorney General's Office Asset Recovery Agency.

The validity and legitimacy criteria of the data in this research are maintained through document triangulation and normative confirmation, namely by comparing laws and regulations, scientific literature, and legal practices in the field, so that the conclusions produced are objective, valid, and can be accounted for academically and legally (Muhtar, 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The Nature of Handling Confiscated and Seized Goods from a Social Justice Perspective

The handling of confiscated and seized goods is not merely part of formal legal procedures within the criminal justice system, but also carries profound moral, social, and philosophical dimensions. In the context of economic crimes such as corruption, money laundering, and transnational organized crime, the state cannot simply impose criminal sanctions on perpetrators. Assets obtained from the proceeds of crime must be traced, confiscated, and returned to the state as a means of reparation for losses and the restoration of violated public rights. Therefore, confiscation and confiscation are not merely repressive measures, but also concrete efforts to restore social justice (Fuadi et al., 2024).

The basic philosophy of asset confiscation can be traced to the teachings of restorative justice, which emphasizes the restoration of social relationships damaged by criminal acts. In this approach, victims, perpetrators, and the state engage in a just recovery process, where asset restitution is a crucial element in restoring conditions to their original state (*restitutio in integrum*). This differs from the retributive approach, which focuses solely on punishment.

In restorative justice, the primary focus is on repair and restoration, so the management of confiscated and seized assets must be directed toward returning economic and symbolic benefits to the wider community (Kirkwood, 2022; Marshall, 2020; Van Ness et al., 2022).

From a sociological perspective, economically motivated crimes have a systemic impact on society. The accumulation of wealth obtained illegally by criminals often undermines the principle of distributive justice and reinforces economic inequality. When perpetrators continue to enjoy the proceeds of their crimes, society's sense of justice is undermined, public trust in the legal system is weakened, and the state's legitimacy is questioned. Therefore, returning assets to the state is not only a matter of budget recovery, but also of restoring public trust in the law and government.

The handling of confiscated objects is also closely linked to the constitutional principles of Article 28D paragraph (1) and Article 28H paragraph (4) of the 1945 Constitution, which guarantee the right to legal protection and property rights that cannot be taken arbitrarily. Therefore, confiscation must be carried out based on fair and proportional laws and uphold the principle of due process of law (Wulandari et al., 2025). On the one hand, the state is obliged to protect the public interest from the dangers of crime; on the other hand, individual rights must be respected. This is where the challenge of a state under the rule of law lies: harmonizing the protection of individual rights with the fulfillment of collective interests.

Confiscated and seized assets, if not managed properly, can become a burden on the state. Many cases demonstrate that confiscated assets that are not immediately utilized or confiscated end up damaged, abandoned, or lose their value. This demonstrates the importance of an efficient and measurable management system. Furthermore, confiscation also has a preventive effect, creating a deterrent effect on potential criminals who realize that the proceeds of their crimes will not be enjoyed. In this regard, the handling of confiscated assets becomes a tool to enforce social norms and internalize legal values within society.

Furthermore, in the context of a welfare state, the state has a responsibility not only to enforce the law but also to ensure that the proceeds of crime are returned and utilized to the maximum extent possible for the prosperity of the people. Therefore, assets successfully confiscated and confiscated from criminals must be managed, utilized, and/or auctioned to support the financing of public programs such as education, health, and infrastructure. Thus, asset confiscation becomes a legally valid and socially meaningful instrument of economic redistribution (Kartika et al., 2021).

From a modern criminal law perspective, confiscation and forfeiture also play a crucial role in asset-oriented criminal justice, which focuses not only on the criminal behavior but also on the instruments, proceeds, and economic value of the crime. This approach allows for more effective law enforcement because it not only restricts the perpetrator's freedom but also halts the flow of economic benefits derived from criminal activity. Therefore, the nature of handling confiscated and seized objects cannot be separated from the broader agenda of legal development that promotes social justice and the protection of state resources.

2. Attribution Authority of the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA)

The Asset Recovery Agency (BPA) of the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia is an institutional entity that obtains attributional authority from statutory regulations, specifically based on Article 30A of Law Number 11 of 2021 concerning Amendments to Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia. This provision emphasizes that the Attorney General's Office has the duty and authority to carry out asset recovery originating from criminal acts. Furthermore, the institutional strengthening of the BPA is also regulated in Presidential Regulation Number 15 of 2024, which establishes it as a supporting element of the Attorney General's duties and authorities in the field of asset recovery, and is technically regulated within the organizational structure of the Attorney General's Office through the Attorney General's Regulation.

The attribution authority held by the BPA covers various important stages in asset recovery: asset tracing, blocking/freezing, confiscation, confiscation through court decisions, and the return of assets to the state or the rightful party. This authority is not granted through delegation or administrative mandate, but rather stems directly from valid legal norms, demonstrating that the BPA is an entity with strong legal standing. This emphasizes the BPA's strategic position as an institution with operational capacity and legal jurisdiction in the criminal law enforcement process based on the recovery of state losses (Pakaja et al., 2025).

Legally, this attribution authority legitimizes the BPA to act in all stages of asset recovery without having to wait for or be subject to intermediary bureaucracy. Thus, the BPA has institutional autonomy and a control function over the process of executing assets recovered from crime. This role is not only administrative but also involves investigative and litigative work. The BPA can collaborate with investigators and prosecutors to ensure that assets related to criminal acts can be effectively traced from the beginning of the legal process (Afrian et al., 2025). The BPA's authority also implies that this institution is responsible for cross-sector coordination with various related institutions, such as the Police, the Courts, the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (in the context of RUPBASAN), and the Ministry of Finance through the DJKN. In practice, the BPA not only handles assets in the form of movable and immovable property within the country, but can also establish international cooperation in the context of cross-jurisdictional asset recovery based on the principle of mutual legal assistance (MLA) recognized in international conventions and national laws.

More than just a structural entity, the BPA represents a modern approach to asset recovery, one that no longer positions asset recovery as a secondary or incidental function within the legal process, but rather as a key component in recouping state losses. Attribution authority allows the BPA to carry out this role directly and measurably. In fact, in international practice, many countries accord similar status to asset recovery authorities as semi-autonomous institutions standing alongside conventional law enforcement agencies. Indonesia's move through the BPA reflects convergence with this global standard. However, the attribution authority held by the BPA needs to be continuously supported by adequate human resources, an integrated information system, and an adaptive legal framework. Challenges in the field indicate that although the BPA is normatively equipped with strong attribution authority, its implementation still faces technical obstacles, overlapping regulations, and suboptimal synergy between institutions. Therefore, strengthening institutional capacity is an absolute necessity so that this attribution authority can be exercised optimally in the context of law enforcement that not only punishes perpetrators but also safeguards state assets for the greatest possible prosperity of the people.

3. Institutional Transformation from Asset Recovery Center to Asset Recovery Agency (BPA)

The institutional transformation from the Asset Recovery Center (PPA) to the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA) within the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia reflects a shift in the paradigm of law enforcement, which is no longer solely oriented toward punishing perpetrators but also emphasizes optimizing the recovery of state assets as part of a modern,

transparent, and equitable legal system. Previously, the PPA was a functional work unit at the echelon II level, directly reporting to the Deputy Attorney General for Development. This structural limitation resulted in minimal institutional impetus, weak inter-agency coordination, and suboptimal handling of confiscated and seized assets, particularly in major and cross-border cases. The transformation into the BPA is based on Prosecutor's Regulation Number 3 of 2024 and reinforced by Presidential Regulation Number 15 of 2024. Under this regulation, the BPA was elevated to an echelon I unit directly under the Attorney General. Its organizational structure includes the Agency Secretariat, the Asset Tracking and Confiscation Management Center, the Asset Rescue Center, and functional position groups. This elevation in institutional status is not only a form of administrative reform but also a response to the need for more coordinated, efficient, and integrated information system-based state asset management.

The BPA's primary function is to serve as a national coordination hub in the asset recovery process. The BPA serves not only as a technical implementer but also as a formulator of internal Prosecutor's Office policies regarding the tracing, securing, and repatriation of criminal assets. This model aligns with international practice, which establishes asset recovery institutions as separate authorities with comprehensive legal and administrative powers. The BPA is tasked with processing confiscated assets from the pretrial stage, ensuring the continuity of the legal process, managing the confiscated proceeds, and distributing them to the state or the authorized parties in accordance with court decisions (Sofwan et al., 2019).

This transformation is also supported by the development of information technology such as the Integrated Asset Recovery System (IARS), which enables digital asset management from tracking to execution. This system is integrated with the RUPBASAN (Regional Asset Management Agency), the DJKN (Directorate General of State Assets), and related financial institutions to ensure data accuracy and accountability in every process. BPA also initiated international collaboration through Mutual Legal Assistance schemes and cross-jurisdictional asset tracing, particularly in cases of Money Laundering (TPPU) and cross-border corruption.

One of the advantages of the BPA compared to its predecessor is its stronger institutional authority to facilitate coordination between ministries/agencies. Previously, the PPA's role relied heavily on goodwill between agencies, without a clear structural and legal framework. Now, the BPA has a position that allows for direct coordination with the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (managing the RUPBASAN), the Ministry of Finance (managing the State Assets/DJKN), as well as the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK), the National Police (Polri), and the Financial Transaction Reports and Analysis Center (PPATK). This strength provides a crucial foundation for building a robust and measurable national asset recovery system. However, this transformation is not without challenges. Some of the challenges faced include bureaucratic resistance, the need for standardized SOPs across institutions, the need for increased human resource capacity, and consistent operational funding. Furthermore, in the long term, the BPA must be able to demonstrate its effectiveness through significant and transparent asset return performance, so that it does not become a mere formality.

Thus, the institutional transformation from the PPA to the BPA represents a significant step forward in the history of law enforcement in Indonesia. This step not only strengthens the Attorney General's Office in its role as *dominus litis*, but also makes asset recovery a strategic agenda for safeguarding state finances, achieving social justice, and restoring public trust in the rule of law.

4. Problems and Obstacles in Implementing Asset Recovery

Although the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA) was established with a strong legal basis and a more robust institutional structure than its predecessor, the implementation of asset recovery in Indonesia still faces various substantial issues and operational constraints. These problems are not only internal to the institution but also involve cross-institutional coordination, unclear legal norms, and challenges within an implementation system that is not yet optimally integrated.

One of the main obstacles is overlapping authority between institutions. Normatively, the management of confiscated and seized assets involves more than one institution, such as the Attorney General's Office (through the BPA), the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (through the RUPBASAN), and the Ministry of Finance (through the DJKN). However, in practice, there is no solid coordination framework and standard protocols between these institutions. As a result, asset management is often asynchronous, even giving rise to disputes between institutions regarding the legal status and authority to manage evidence and seized assets that have become final and binding.

Furthermore, the asset recovery system also faces obstacles in the form of incomplete regulations, particularly regarding the mechanism for non-conviction-based forfeiture. Law Number 8 of 2010 concerning the Eradication of Money Laundering provides a basis for asset confiscation without having to wait for a criminal verdict against the perpetrator, but its implementation in the field is still hampered by procedural provisions that require prior proof of the predicate offense. This makes the asset recovery process very lengthy and full of uncertainty. Complex and bureaucratic procedures are also a crucial obstacle. Asset recovery must go through a lengthy process, from investigation and prosecution to final decisions, and finally execution through the executive branch. In many cases, confiscated assets become worthless or damaged before they can be returned to the state treasury. The lack of a flexible interim management mechanism leaves the state burdened with high maintenance costs for confiscated assets without any commensurate returns. This situation is exacerbated by limited storage facilities, such as inadequate storage capacity at the RUPBASAN (State Treasury) and weak long-term oversight of confiscated assets. Another issue is the limited ability to trace assets across jurisdictions, particularly in large-scale money laundering and corruption cases involving the transfer of funds abroad. Indonesia has been a member of the Mutual Legal Assistance (MLA) regime, but administrative processes and cross-border cooperation are often hampered by differences in legal systems, the principle of sovereignty, and a lack of response from the destination country. This results in many assets known to be located abroad failing to be recovered, even after a final and binding court decision.

Another obstacle is the low human resource capacity and technological infrastructure of law enforcement agencies, including the Attorney General's Office. Asset recovery requires multidisciplinary expertise, spanning criminal law, civil law, forensic auditing, finance, and digital tracking.

Unfortunately, not all work units have adequate technically competent human resources. Existing information technology is also not fully integrated across agencies, resulting in inaccurate and non-real-time asset management and reporting. This weakness opens up the potential for data manipulation and a lack of transparency in the distribution or auction of seized assets.

Finally, there are also obstacles related to legal culture and bureaucratic resistance. Not all law enforcement officials have made asset recovery a strategic priority. Many still view this process as merely an adjunct to punishing perpetrators, rather than a core component of ensuring state justice. This mindset often delays or results in the asset tracing and confiscation process being inadequately implemented. Furthermore, bureaucratic resistance to structural reforms, including the allocation of authority and budgets, has hampered the strengthening of the national asset recovery system.

Considering all these constraints, a more adaptive and integrated reformulation of legal and governance approaches is necessary. Asset recovery cannot simply rely on strengthening institutions like the BPA; it also requires systemic reforms to the legal framework, inter-institutional coordination, process digitization, and increased awareness and capacity of legal actors. Without these, asset recovery has the potential to stagnate and fail to address the evolving needs for economic justice in the dynamics of modern crime.

5. Inter-Institutional Settlement Model in Management of Confiscated and Confiscated Objects

Effective management of confiscated and seized assets requires a settlement model capable of bridging the fragmented authority between law enforcement agencies and state asset managers. In the Indonesian context, regulatory complexity and weak coordination between institutions such as the Attorney General's Office (BPA), the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (RUPBASAN), and the Ministry of Finance (DJKN) create an urgent need to establish an integrated, accountable, and equitable inter-institutional settlement model. This model not only simplifies the confiscation and execution mechanisms but also ensures efficiency and optimizes the economic benefits of state-controlled assets. The ideal settlement model must first be built on the foundation of an integrated legal framework, which clearly regulates the communication flow and working authority of each institution.

Currently, overlapping provisions between the Criminal Procedure Code (KUHP), the Attorney General's Law, the Money Laundering Law, and internal regulations such as the Attorney General's Regulation and the Presidential Regulation create confusion in implementation. Therefore, an umbrella regulation—in the form of a Presidential Regulation or a specific law on asset recovery—is needed to serve as a single reference throughout the entire process of handling confiscated and seized objects.

Second, an inter-institutional coordination and collaboration mechanism is needed that is institutional in nature, not ad hoc. This can be implemented through the establishment of a Joint Asset Recovery Task Force consisting of representatives from the Attorney General's Office, the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, the Police, the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK), the Financial Transaction Reports and Analysis Center (PPATK), and the Directorate General of State Assets (DJKN). This team must have a mandate to handle strategic cases, coordinate the asset tracing and execution process, and ensure that seized assets can be promptly utilized or returned. The existence of this cross-sectoral team will also reduce the risk of duplication, expedite decision-making, and increase public accountability.

Third, the success of this model depends heavily on the digitization and integration of cross-agency information systems. Systems such as the Integrated Asset Recovery System (IARS) developed by the BPA must be connected to the information systems of the RUPBASAN (State-Owned Financial Institutions Agency) and the DJKN (Directorate General of State Assets), including the PPATK (Financial Transaction Reports and Analysis Center) for tracking suspicious financial transactions. This system must be able to provide real-time data on the legal status of assets, their storage locations, their economic value, and the status of execution and distribution of proceeds. With this data transparency, the public and supervisory agencies can exercise control and promote transparency in the management of state assets derived from crime.

Fourth, this settlement model must also provide a mechanism for the temporary, legal and productive use of confiscated assets. This is crucial given that many assets depreciate in value due to lack of immediate use. With proper legal basis and oversight, assets such as vehicles, property, or industrial products can be temporarily used by the state or public institutions, for example, as official vehicles or educational facilities. Asset leasing schemes or asset management agreements can be implemented as interim solutions until a final court decision is made.

Fifth, it is also crucial to have technical guidelines or national SOPs that detail the workflow, timelines, and forms of coordination between institutions. These SOPs must be binding and cover all stages, from seizure by investigators, storage by the RUPBASAN, transfer of status to the BPA, and transfer or utilization by the DJKN. In the event of conflicts or obstacles, these SOPs must provide a forum for resolving administrative or policy disputes to avoid unnecessary bureaucratic bottlenecks.

Sixth, independent monitoring and evaluation of this settlement model is necessary, both by the internal inspectorates of each institution, the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK), and external oversight bodies such as the Prosecutorial Commission or the Ombudsman. This oversight is crucial to ensure that the asset management process is not abused and that the proceeds of asset recovery are truly returned to the public interest. Transparency in reporting to the public, including through an open online portal, will strengthen public trust in Indonesia's law enforcement system.

Thus, the ideal inter-institutional settlement model should reflect the principles of institutional synergy, be based on an integrated information system, possess legal certainty, and prioritize efficiency and public benefit. Within this framework, the Asset Recovery Agency serves as the primary driver of asset recovery policy integration, serving not only as an administrative executor but also as a system designer that ensures every rupiah of criminal proceeds is returned to finance justice and welfare.

6. Strategic Solutions: Direction of Asset Recovery Reform

In response to the various structural, procedural, and substantive obstacles that still plague asset recovery in Indonesia, a series of comprehensive, progressive, and sustainable strategic solutions are needed. Asset recovery reforms should not simply strengthen institutions, such as the establishment of the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA), but must also encompass legal framework reforms, strengthening human resource capacity, modernizing information systems, and developing responsive and results-oriented cross-agency governance. Without these strategic steps, asset recovery will become merely an administrative formality that lacks a tangible impact on social justice and the country's economic recovery. The most urgent first solution is the ratification and implementation of the Asset Forfeiture Law, which specifically and explicitly regulates the non-conviction-based asset forfeiture mechanism. This law should provide a strong legal basis for the state to seize and confiscate assets without the need for complex and lengthy criminal proceedings, provided that the assets are legally and convincingly proven to originate from illegal activities. Countries such as the United States, Australia, and Switzerland have proven this mechanism effective in crippling organized crime syndicates and returning the proceeds of crime to society.

The second solution is to restructure technical regulations that have overlapped and restricted each other between institutions. The government, through the coordinating role of the Coordinating Ministry for Political, Legal, and Security Affairs (Kemenko Polhukam), needs to facilitate the development of a Presidential Regulation or Joint Regulation across ministries/institutions as a single procedural reference for managing confiscated and seized assets. This will eliminate ambiguity in the implementation of duties and avoid conflicts of authority between the Prosecutor's Office, the Police, the RUPBASAN (State Budget Agency), and the DJKN (Directorate General of State Assets).

Third, strengthening the BPA as a professional and technology-based asset recovery institution is key to long-term reform. The BPA needs to be developed not merely as an administrative unit, but as a center of excellence with a forensic audit team, financial analysts, international legal specialists, and an integrated digital information system manager. The BPA must be capable of tracing domestic and foreign assets, managing evidence with high economic value, and building strategic global partnerships for extradition and asset recovery across jurisdictions.

The fourth solution concerns strengthening human resource (HR) capacity. Prosecutors, investigators, and confiscated assets managers require specialized training in asset tracing, financial investigations, evidence management, and international cooperation. These training

programs should be facilitated nationally and sustainably, in collaboration with international institutions such as the UNODC, the World Bank StAR Initiative, and Interpol. With trained human resources, the asset recovery process will be more effective, faster, and minimize procedural errors.

Fifth, developing an integrated and transparent national information system is a prerequisite for digital reform. Systems such as the Integrated Asset Recovery System (IARS) must be connected to data on land ownership, vehicles, bank accounts, companies, and even digital assets like cryptocurrency. These systems must also be equipped with artificial intelligence (AI)-based asset tracking algorithms that can analyze suspicious transaction patterns in real time. Openness of these systems to the public and supervisory agencies will strengthen institutional trust and accountability.

The sixth solution is the productive use of assets during the transition period before the final court decision. The state can regulate asset utilization or temporary use schemes based on prudential principles. For example, property can be leased, vehicles can be used for public services, or digital assets can be safely included in state financial management. This approach not only preserves asset value but also contributes to the economy during the lengthy legal process.

Ultimately, a social justice and public benefit approach must underpin all solutions. Asset recovery is not just about legal or fiscal aspects, but also about restoring a sense of justice to the community and improving state-people relations. Therefore, proceeds from asset recovery should be allocated to priority programs such as education, healthcare, and village infrastructure. This way, communities will directly benefit from law enforcement, and this will be a strong driver for the sustainability of comprehensive asset recovery reforms. (Suriani et al., 2025).

CONCLUSION

Asset recovery from criminal activity is a strategic component of modern law enforcement, focusing not only on punishing perpetrators but also on recovering state losses and restoring social justice. The establishment of the Asset Recovery Agency (BPA) within the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia reflects an institutional transformation that strengthens the role of the prosecutor's office as the primary actor in managing confiscated and seized assets. However, the effectiveness of the BPA still faces structural, regulatory, and technical challenges, particularly in terms of inter-agency coordination, limited regulations on confiscation without criminal prosecution, and low capacity for cross-jurisdictional asset tracing. Therefore, comprehensive reform is needed through strengthening the legal basis, integrating information systems, training human resources, and establishing an adaptive inter-agency settlement model. With a structured, collaborative, and technology-based approach, asset recovery can be a crucial instrument in strengthening the rule of law, restoring public trust, and achieving sustainable community welfare.

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